

A Temporal Model of Learner Behavior in an Immersive Virtual Reality Learning Environment Using Process Mining

Antony Prakash

*Interdisciplinary Program in Educational Technology
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay
Mumbai, India
antony80004@gmail.com*

Ramkumar Rajendran

*Interdisciplinary Program in Educational Technology
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay
Mumbai, India
ramkumar.rajendran@iitb.ac.in*

Abstract—The advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has paved the way for the integration of cutting-edge immersive Virtual Reality (VR) in education. Existing research studies in the field of education have explored the use of immersive VR technology and have examined its impact on learning outcomes, engagement, and the overall learning experience. These studies typically involve conducting experiments and collecting data through questionnaires, surveys, and interviews, as well as quantitative methods like pre-tests and post-tests, physiological sensors, eye trackers, and tracking the orientation of head-mounted display (HMD) and hand-held controllers (HHC). We collected interaction data of 14 undergraduate non-electrical students, while they interacted with MaroonVR, a Virtual Reality Learning Environment (VRLE) designed to teach the physics concept of electromagnetic induction. This paper aims to analyze the differences in interaction patterns between high performers and low performers and to identify the temporal sequence of actions that contribute to high performance using a process modeling approach. To achieve this, we employed a fuzzy mining algorithm to analyze the logged interaction trace data collected through our Interaction Behavior Data (IBD) collection mechanism. Unique interaction behavior models were developed for both high performers and low performers. These behavior models offer deeper insights into the differences in behavior exhibited by high and low performers. We propose that the findings of this study can be utilized to provide guidelines to VR learning content developers, enabling them to create immersive VRLEs that can offer adaptive personalized feedback, hints, and VR learning content based on learners' interaction behavior.

Index Terms—Immersive Virtual Reality, Educational Data Mining, Interaction Tracking, Behavioral Data Logging, Process Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

The progress of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has opened up new possibilities for incorporating cutting-edge immersive technologies into the field of education. These technologies include Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR) [13]. VR involves creating 3D virtual worlds that mimic real or imaginary environments, allowing users to experience them

firsthand. AR integrates virtual objects into the real world or vice versa, accessible even through mobile devices. MR, on the other hand, represents a continuum between reality and virtuality. In education, VR and AR have been widely utilized, while MR is also gaining popularity but not as extensively as VR and AR. The focus of this paper is to explore the learning processes that result from the application of state-of-the-art VR in education. VR can be divided into two categories: non-immersive VR and immersive VR [5], [13]. Non-immersive VR involves viewing a synthetic 3D virtual world on a computer screen and interacting with it using a mouse and keyboard. In immersive VR the users wear a head-mounted display (HMD) and use hand-held controllers (HHC) to interact with the 3D virtual world from a first-person perspective [2], [7]. The current study specifically concentrates on the educational applications of immersive VR.

In educational research, most studies experiment with immersive VR to gauge its impact on user experience. They analyze learning outcomes (knowledge and skill acquisition, retention, and transfer) [4] and affective states (engagement, confusion, frustration, boredom) [3]. Data collection methods for such analyses included:

- User experience: Data was gathered through self-reported questionnaires, interviews, and surveys [11].
- Affective states: Data collection for affective states involved both questionnaires and physiological sensors [4].
- Learning outcomes: Data was obtained through pre-test, post-test, and delayed post-test evaluations.

While existing tools effectively assess learning outcomes, they fall short in elucidating the learning process during VR intervention. Crucial questions about how learners acquire knowledge, which behaviors influence outcomes, and whether behavioral changes affect learning remain unanswered. Consequently, the VR intervention's learning process remains poorly understood. To bridge this gap, we developed a mechanism to log button clicks, virtual object interactions, and timestamps, akin to click stream data logs in computer-based learning environments (CBLE). This mechanism was applied in MaroonVR

[8], a VR learning environment for electromagnetic induction physics concepts.

In our study, we had 14 participants and collected their interaction trace data. We extracted action events from these traces and did correlation and regression analysis. However, this approach may not fully reveal the temporal action sequence or performance patterns. Therefore, in this paper, we explore a process mining approach to uncover significant differences in action sequences between high and low performers.

The paper's following sections address distinct research aspects. Section 2 reviews process mining in educational data. Section 3 outlines the methodology, study design, IBD logger data, and extracted action events for process mining. Section 4 presents process models and an in-depth analysis of high and low performers. Section 5 concludes, noting study limitations and suggesting future research directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The IBD logging mechanism, which captures comprehensive information about interaction traces, virtual objects interactions, and timestamps, proves valuable in deriving essential behavioral artifacts like the duration of action events and their sequence of execution by learners in the VR Learning Environment (VRLE). Consequently, process mining can be applied to the sequential action events extracted from the logged IBD. This approach provides deeper insights into learners' behavior within the VRLE, aiding in understanding the learning process and discerning differences in the learning process between high performers and low performers. Since no prior studies on process mining in the context of VRLE are available, we conducted a search for research articles that discuss process mining in computer-based learning environments (CBLE). Below, we will discuss three articles that employed process mining techniques in CBLEs for various purposes.

In a prior study by Juhaňák et al. (2019) [6], process mining methods were applied to analyze students' behavior in online quizzes, categorizing actions such as "attempting all questions," "skipping questions," and "giving up." They observed that the frequency of these interaction sequences varied based on the quiz difficulty and the student's prior knowledge.

Similarly, Cerezo et al. (2020) [1] utilized process mining methods to evaluate students' self-regulated learning (SRL) skills in e-learning environments. They identified various behavioral patterns, such as "goal-setting," "planning," "monitoring," and "regulation," and found that the frequency of these patterns differed according to students' SRL skills.

In another study by Rajendran et al. (2018) [12], process mining was employed to construct temporal models of learners' behavior in Betty's Brain, an Open-Ended Learning Environment (OELE). Betty's Brain facilitates student learning of scientific processes through building causal models. The process mining approach was used to distinguish behavior patterns between high and low performers in the OELE.

Previous studies in CBLE revealed the use of process mining algorithms like alpha miner, heuristic miner, and fuzzy

Fig. 1. Scenes in VRLE

miner [12]. They developed distinct process models for high and low performers, offering insights into action sequence differences [6], [12]. This information is instrumental in identifying the specific sequence of interaction behaviors that correlates with high and low performance respectively.

From the knowledge gained in literature analysis, in our study, we applied a fuzzy mining algorithm to create process models. These models help us understand temporal differences in interaction behavior between high and low performers. With insights from these models, we can design VRLE with adaptive scaffolds to improve learning outcomes.

III. METHODOLOGY

In a previous study, we provided a detailed explanation of the IBD logging mechanism and the information it captures [9]. Additionally, we described MaroonVR [8], VRLE used to learn several physics concepts including electromagnetic induction, and in which we deployed the developed IBD logging mechanism [10]. Electromagnetic induction is a phenomenon where moving a magnet in close proximity to a coil induces an electromotive force (emf). For our study, we utilized three scenes from MaroonVR as shown in Fig 1 to explore this concept:

- Faraday's Law Experiment: In this scene, learners grabbed and dragged the magnet inside the coil to generate emf.
- Falling Coil Experiment: Learners observed emf by allowing the magnet and an iron bar to fall freely inside the coil.
- Perspective Scene: In this scene, learners assumed the perspective of the magnet and generated emf through their physical walking.

Throughout these scenes, learners could interact with virtual interfaces to vary the coil turns (2, 4, and 6 turns), coil diameter (2, 4, and 6 units), and magnetic field strength. The learners could also perform actions such as grabbing, dragging, dropping the magnet, and walking in the perspective scene. The learning follows embodied cognition as the learners tend to make meaning by interacting through their bodily actions. All the interactions were logged in the IBD logger. The IBD

logger is a .csv file that has column headers as 1) HHC used (right and left), 2) Buttons in the HHC used, 3) Actions performed with the HHC buttons (clicked, released, etc.), 4) Button pressure, 5) Thumbstick axes, 6) Thumbstick angle, 7) Virtual objects interacted with, and 8) Timestamp.

This comprehensive data allows us to analyze learners' interactions in the VRLE and gain valuable insights into their behavior during the learning process.

TABLE I
ACTION EVENTS EXTRACTED FROM THE IBD LOGGER AND THEIR DESCRIPTION

Action Events	Description
INFO	Reading instruction
NAVIGATE	Teleport, Scene switching
INTERACT_REL	Handling virtual objects such as magnet and iron bar (interacted using Grip button)
PERS_WALK	Walking in the perspective scene taking the perspective of magnet
SET_COIL_REL	Setting the turns in the coil between 2 turns, 4 turns and 6 turns (interacted using Trigger button)
SET_MAG_REL	Varying the magnetic field strength using VR slider interface (interacted using Trigger button)
SET_COIL_IRREL	Setting the coil turns using HHC buttons other than Trigger button causing no interaction
SET_MAG_IRREL	Setting the magnetic field strength using HHC buttons other than Trigger button causing no interaction
INTERACT_IRREL	Handling magnet and iron bar using HHC buttons other than Grip button causing no interaction

We conducted a study involving 14 undergraduate students majoring in fields other than electrical engineering. The participants' demographic details were collected, and their prior knowledge of electromagnetic induction was assessed through a pre-test. Before experiencing the VRLE, the participants played a VR game called 'First Steps' to familiarize themselves with the Hand-Held Controller (HHC) buttons and VR interactions. During the VRLE experience, the interaction behavior of each participant was automatically logged in the IBD logger. Later, various action events were extracted from the IBD logger and are presented in Table I. Following the VR intervention, a post-test was administered to measure the learning gain. To analyze the action events mentioned in Table I, we employed process mining with a fuzzy mining algorithm.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants were divided into two groups: high performers and low performers, based on their post-test scores ($M=7.64$, $SD=2.06$) [10]. The 8 participants who scored above the mean score were categorized as high performers and the rest 6 were considered low performers. The resulting process models for high performers and low performers after applying process mining are shown in Fig 2.

The process models of both high and low performers exhibit similarities in certain behaviors. Specifically, cyclic execution of action events between 1) SET_MAGNET_REL and SET_MAGNET_IRREL, 2) SET_COIL_REL and SET_COIL_IRREL, and 3) INTERACT_REL and INTERACT_IRREL is evident in both groups' process

models. The irrelevant actions (SET_COIL_IRREL, SET_MAGNET_IRREL, INTERACT_IRREL) are logged when participants press irrelevant buttons on the HHCs while trying to perform the interactive actions in the VRLE. However, no actual interaction occurs in the VRLE as a result of pressing these irrelevant HHC buttons. These common cyclic patterns found in the process models of both high and low performers suggest that both groups struggled and lacked experience in interacting with VR technology.

In the interaction behavior model of high performers, as shown in Fig 2 (left), we observed a repeated cyclic execution of action events, particularly "SET_COIL_REL" and "INTERACT_REL." Additionally, they exhibited a linear execution pattern, performing actions in the sequence of "SET_MAG_REL" followed by "SET_COIL_REL" and then "INTERACT_REL." This indicates that high performers first varied the magnetic strength and the number of turns of the coil before moving the magnet in and out of the coil. Moreover, they engaged in repeated cyclic interactions with the magnet and coil turns.

Conversely, such well-structured executions were not evident among the low performers as shown in Fig 2 (right). In their interaction behavior model, there was no node linked to the node representing "INTERACT_REL." This suggests that low performers did not perform any action events before interacting with the magnet to move it in and out of the coil. The absence of a preceding action event indicates a lack of meaningful planning or sequencing in their interactions compared to the high performers.

Both high performers and low performers start their interaction with the VRLE by reading the provided instructions, as indicated by the action event INFO. Afterward, the behaviors of both groups show similarities and differences. For high performers, their subsequent actions involve navigating or interacting with the coil to set its parameters. On the other hand, low performers navigate in the environment before setting either the coil parameters or the magnet parameters.

Further analysis reveals that high performers, after setting the coil parameters, proceed to set the magnet field strength and interact with the magnet to induce emf. They also navigate and enter the perspective scene. Moreover, high performers, after setting the magnet parameters or after interacting with the magnet to induce emf, go back to setting the coil parameters. This demonstrates a clear pattern of high performers repeatedly engaging in actions related to setting both coil and magnet parameters and interacting with the magnet to induce emf.

In contrast, low performers, after setting the coil parameter, mainly proceed to enter the perspective scene, similar to some high performers, and do not perform any other interactive actions. Additionally, low performers set the coil parameters after setting the magnet, following a pattern observed in high performers.

Overall, the process models for high performers reveal more deliberate and thoughtful interaction behavior, involving variations in magnetic strength, coil turns, and repeated inter-

Fig. 2. Process Model of High Performers (left) and Low Performers (right)

actions with the magnet. In contrast, the process models for low performers indicate a more random and less organized approach to interactions, with a lack of meaningful actions before engaging with the magnet.

V. CONCLUSION

The lack of process modeling literature in VRLE, has made us adapt process modeling approaches used in CBLE and apply it to VRLE logs. We employed a fuzzy mining algorithm for analyzing VRLE log data's action events. The findings highlighted distinct interaction patterns: High performers repeatedly and cyclically executed actions of setting the parameters of coil and magnet, and interaction with magnet, contributing to their success. In contrast, low performers lacked these patterns in their interactions.

These key differences in learning behavior offer valuable information to design personalized feedback and scaffolding for learners in VRLE. However, the study has certain limitations. The small sample size of only 14 participants and the homogeneity of the learners, who were all computer science engineering undergraduate students from the same college and age group, may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, using only the fuzzy mining algorithm as the process mining technique might affect the study's predictability and general applicability.

The study offers insights into action event frequency and duration in VRLE and its link to performance. The process models highlight interaction differences between high and low performers, revealing VRLE learning processes. Next, we propose the implementation of personalized feedback and scaffolding based on these patterns in future research.

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